

EFFECT OF INTRAVENOUS PUSH ANTIBIOTICS ADMINISTRATION SAFETY GUIDELINES ON NURSES' PERFORMANCE AT ONE UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL

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Abstract

Background: Intravenous antibiotics push are one of the top medication classes resulting in emergency department visits for adverse drug events while Medications errors occur due to reasons as lack of nurses' knowledge regarding drug preparation and administration also nurses noncompliance with safety guidelines. Hence, nurses are responsible for the administration of intravenous (IV) push antibiotics in accordance with these guidelines that will improve patients' outcomes. Little studies were conducted to evaluate the effect of intravenous antibiotics push medications safety guidelines on nurses' performance. The aim of the study was to evaluate the effect of intravenous push antibiotics administration safety guidelines on nurses' performance. **Methods:** Pre-posttest quasi experimental research design was used. Sample of all nurses' work in medical and surgical wards. The researcher collected data through using Nurses' Demographic Data Sheet, Intravenous Antibiotic Administration nurses' knowledge Questionnaire, IV Push/Bolus Antibiotics Administration related Nurse's Attitude Questionnaire and IV push/bolus antibiotics administration nurses' observational Checklist. **Results:** There were highly statistically significant differences in nurses' total knowledge mean scores pre and post implementation of safety guidelines. ($X^2 = 5.811, P = 0.001$) ($X^2 = 5.152, P = 0.001$). Pre-intervention, 70 % of the studied nurses have an unsatisfactory knowledge level while post intervention, 80 % of the studied nurses have satisfactory knowledge level. Concerning nurses' attitude. there was high statistically significant difference in total nurses' attitude score between pre and post implementation of safety guidelines at $p \leq 0.05$. 86,7% among the studied nurses has un satisfactory level of attitude pre implementation of safety guidelines, while 66.7% report satisfactory level of attitude post implementation of safety guidelines, regarding nurses practices the study showed that in relation to preparing sterile water from ampule 83.3%unsatisfactory practice pre intervention while 66.7% satisfactory practice post intervention, concerning preparing antibiotic from vial 80.0% unsatisfactory practice pre intervention while 80.0% satisfactory practice post intervention, as regard to IV administration via bolus or push 76.7 %unsatisfactory practice pre intervention while 73.3% satisfactory practice post intervention, there was a high statistically significant difference in the total nurses practice score pre and post implementation of Safety Guidelines at $p \leq 0.05$. **Conclusions:** Intravenous push antibiotics administration safety guidelines had a positive effect on nurses' performance, so it is

recommended that IV push antibiotic administration safety guidelines be applied in all health care facilities to achieve high quality patient care.

Keywords: Intravenous push, Antibiotics Administration, Safety Guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

Intravenous therapy and medicines (IVTM) play an essential role in the treatment of illness, management of chronic conditions and in maintaining health and wellbeing. With up to 90% of admitted patients now receiving IVTM at some point while they are in the hospital, relevant guidelines are more necessary than ever ^[1].

Intravenous antibiotics IV bolus / push are one of the top medication classes resulting in emergency department visits for adverse drug events (ADEs). Also, an allergic reaction is the most common type of antibiotic-associated adverse drug event ^[2]. Moreover, medications errors (MEs) occur due to many reasons, such as lack of knowledge, increased workload and noncompliance with guidelines. Most of the errors occur during the medicine administration stage. Although MEs may occur by different health care professionals, the occurrence of MEs is high in nursing ^[3].

Intravenous antibiotics administration safety guidelines which are set of evidence-based practices concerning drug dose/ concentration, compatible fluid, volume, method of administration, duration and special nursing considerations that nurses and all healthcare professionals need to follow to ensure patient safety and improve patients' outcomes. These guidelines consist of guidance statements representing consensus for safe practice associated with IV push/bolus antibiotics preparation and administration in adults. Hence, nurses are responsible for the administration of IV push/bolus in accordance with these guidelines that will improve effectiveness, quality of care, decrease variations in clinical practice as well as the cost ^[4].

Patients' outcomes in the current study refer to complications associated with IV push/bolus antibiotics administration which include allergic reaction, phlebitis, thrombophlebitis, infiltration, pain and death. These complications could be reduced by having safe and effective guidelines on preparation, checking, labelling, prescribing, administration and monitoring of IV push/bolus antibiotics in all clinical areas in order to reduce the rate of medication errors and consequently improve patients' outcomes ^[5].

Nurses have a unique role and responsibility in medication administration in general and IV push/bolus in particular that they are frequently the final person to check to see that the medication is correctly prescribed and dispensed before administration ^[5]. Moreover, nurses' performance involving successful preparation, administration and monitoring IV push/ bolus antibiotics administration through adhering safety practice guidelines ^[6].

The aim of this work was to evaluate the effect of intravenous antibiotics pushing medications safety guidelines on nurses' performance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This pre-posttest quasi experimental study was carried out on 30 nurses, aged from 21 to 45 years old, both sexes, who are working in medical and surgical wards at Kafr Elsheikh University Hospitals, level of education either bachelor's degree in nursing or graduate of institute of nursing and had an experience of administering IV medications not less than 6 months. The study included 60 patients, both sexes and who received prescribed IV push/bolus antibiotics namely Cefotaxime, Ceftriaxone and ampicillin /sulbactam in peripheral intravenous catheter (PIVC) for three consecutive days which was inserted in the forearm or the antecubital fossa, insertion using 20–22-gauge needles.

The study was done after approval from Research Ethics Committee of Faculty of Nursing, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt. An informed written consent was obtained from each participant.

Exclusion criteria for patients was the presence of arm cellulitis, burn, arteriovenous fistula, or radical mastectomy in the arm chosen for PIVC insertion, known allergies to the adhesive tape, cerebrovascular accident, known blood infections or paralysis. The first 30 patients received IV push/bolus antibiotics according to the routine hospital care. On the other hand, the second 30 patients received IV push/bolus after the nurses received IV push/bolus administration safety guidelines.

The researcher collected data using: nurses' demographic data sheet which was developed by the researcher and include nurses' demographic data such as age, gender, years of experience, qualifications, job title, and specialty. The second tool was pre/post Intravenous Antibiotic Administration nurses' knowledge Questionnaire was developed by the researcher to assess nurses' knowledge related to safety guidelines IV push/bolus administration of antibiotics and it consisted of 4MCQ questions and 16 true and false questions. Questions cover four sections. section1: Nurses' knowledge about intravenous antibiotic (7 questions), Section 2: Intravenous antibiotic preparation (5 questions), Section 3: Intravenous antibiotic administration (5 questions), Section 4: complications arising from intravenous antibiotic via push or bolus (3 questions) [7]. Scoring system: The total score was calculated according to the following: each correct answer was given 1 point, and zero points were given for incorrect or missed answer. Total score was 20 points equal 100% divided to two levels: unsatisfactory knowledge level (less than 70% equal less than 14 points), satisfactory knowledge level (from $\geq 70\%$ equal 14 points [8]. The third tool was IV Push/Bolus Antibiotics Administration nurses' observational Checklist. It was developed by the researcher to assess nurses' practice regarding IV push/bolus preparation and administration of antibiotics. It included three parts: The first part covered steps preparing sterile water for injection from an ampule; it consists of 7 steps, the second part contained steps of preparing antibiotic from vial; it consisted of 22 steps. The third part allocated IV antibiotic administration via bolus or push. It consisted of 31 steps [9]. The total score was calculated according to the following: each correct answer was given 1 point, and zero point was given for incorrect or missed answer. The total score was 60 points equal 100% divided into two levels: unsatisfactory

practice level (less than 75% equal less than 45 points), satisfactory practice level (75% equal 45 points) ^[10]. The fourth tool was pre/post IV Push/Bolus Antibiotics Administration related Nurse's Attitude Questionnaire. It was developed by the researcher to assess nurse's attitude toward IV Push/Bolus Administration of Antibiotics. It consisted of 10 statements on positive and negative attitudes for example safe management of IV antibiotics push/bolus administration should be regularly evaluated ^[11]. The total score of attitudes was 10 grades. Each positive attitude was given one grade, and the negative was given zero. It was considered as follows $\geq 75\%$ = positive attitude when the total marks = ≥ 7.5 marks, $< 75\%$ = negative attitude when the total marks = < 7.5 marks ^[12]. The fifth tool was patient demographic and medical data sheet. It was developed by researchers to assess the demographic characteristics of patients, and it included data such as age, gender, place of residence, marital status, education level, work status and smoking habits and the medical data such as the patient's diagnosis, type of antibiotic, indication of antibiotic therapy. The sixth tool was IV Push/Bolus Antibiotics Administration Related Patients' Outcomes Observational Checklist. It was developed by the researcher to assess signs and symptoms related to IV push/bolus administration of antibiotics related complications such as allergic manifestations, phlebitis and infiltration. If the sign occurred, it took score 1 and if not occurs it took score zero.

Procedure

In the preparatory phase, the researcher conducted a review of the pertinent literature regarding intravenous push antibiotics administration safety guidelines and nurses' performance related to IV push/bolus administration of antibiotics. Additionally, the researcher searched for the appropriate tools and seeking expert's advice in addition to obtaining the official permission. In the Implementation phase, the researcher met nurses that are eligible for inclusion criteria face to face in the morning shift. At that time, the purpose and the nature of the study were explained to each potential participant individually, as well as all other ethical considerations mentioned previously being assured. Nurses who agreed to participate in the study were asked to sign the consent form, hence, the researcher asked the nurses to fill out the nurse's demographic data sheet (first tool), pre/post Intravenous Antibiotic Administration nurses' knowledge Questionnaire and the Pre/post IV Push/Bolus Administration of Antibiotics- related Nurse's Attitude Questionnaire. After that the researcher got a list of the patients (control group) who received any of the following intravenous antibiotics: cefotaxime, Ceftriaxone, and ampicillin /sulbactam at 10 am and 12 pm from the head nurse. Then, the researcher chose patients who met the possible inclusion criteria. At that time, the purpose and the nature of the study were explained to each patient individually and filling out the fifth tool and tool number six as well as all other ethical considerations mentioned previously will be assured. Then, the researcher observed and documented nurses' practice during preparation and administration of IV Push/Bolus using Observational Checklist (the third tool). All previous steps considered pre- test or baseline assessment for nurses' performance During this phase the researcher provided IV push/bolus antibiotics administration safety guidelines individually or in a small group for assigned nurses for three consecutive sessions which was equivalent to one session per day, each session

ranged from 30 to 45 minutes. It was provided in the form of a tutorial that give information whilst continually ensuring that nurses comprehend the session content. Each teaching session involved an information part parallel with a practical part. The three sessions were given to nurses as the following: the first session concerned with introduction about IV push/bolus antibiotic medications; factors that increase the risk of IV push/bolus medications errors in adult and safe practice guidelines concerning drug dose/concentration; compatible fluid; volume; method of administration; duration and special nursing considerations for Cefotaxime, Ceftriaxone (information part) while, safe preparation of sterile water for injection from an ampule were the practical part. The second session covered the ten rights of medications and safe practice guidelines mentioned for ampicillin /sulbactam, also aseptic techniques and labeling (information part) and safe preparation of antibiotic from vial as practical part. The third session involved international patient's safety goals and safe practice guidelines regarding administration of IV push/bolus medications while the practical part of the last session was regarding revision of safe preparation and administration of IV push/bolus medications. At the end of the third session intravenous antibiotics safety guidelines handout were given for all nurses and an open discussion was held for any questions. Teaching methods for the information part was group discussion while demonstration and re-demonstration checklist were used for practical part. Suitable teaching aids prepared especially for the intravenous antibiotic safety guidelines such as visual materials were used to facilitate the understanding of the information. Also, revision was carried out regarding all safety guidelines that were previously provided throughout the three educational sessions. One week after the completion of providing safety guidelines, the researcher performed a second assessment (post-test) for nurses' knowledge using the second tool, while the third and the fourth tools (nurses' practice and attitude) were assessed during preparation and administration of IV push/bolus antibiotics administration for patients in the study group who meet inclusion criteria .The evaluation phase was after one week of implementing IV push/bolus antibiotic administration safety guidelines. The researcher assessed nurses' performance (knowledge, practice and attitude).

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was done by SPSS v26 (IBM Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation (SD) and compared between the two groups utilizing unpaired Student's t-test. Qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentage (%) and analyzed using the Chi-square or Fisher's exact test when appropriate. A two-tailed P value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Frequency and percentage distribution of the studied nurses according to demographic characteristics was enumerated in table 1.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of the studied nurses according to demographic characteristics

		N=30
Age (Years):		28.3±3.7
20 – 25		19(63.3%)
26 – 35		11(36.7%)
Sex	Male	8(26.7%)
	Female	22(73.3%)
Unit of specialty	Surgical ward	15(50.0%)
	Medical ward	15(50.0%)
Training courses	No	30(100.0%)
	Yes	0(0.0%)
Qualification	Technical institute	10(33.3%)
	Bachelor	20(66.7%)
Years of experience	Less than 5	24(80.0%)
	5 – 10	6(20.0%)

Data is presented as mean ± SD or frequency (%).

Nurses' knowledge regarding intravenous antibiotic preparation, administration, complications arising from IV antibiotic via push/bolus and total knowledge was significantly improved post-intervention than pre-intervention (P<0.05). **Table 2**

Table 2: Comparison of nurses' knowledge regarding intravenous antibiotic preparation, administration, complications arising from IV antibiotic via push/bolus and total knowledge pre and post implementation of safety guidelines

	Pre-intervention (n=30)	Post-Intervention (n=30)	t	P
Nurses' knowledge about intravenous antibiotics				
Q1. Unasyn is contraindicated in patients with previous history of hepatic dysfunction	12(40.0%)	25 (83.3 %)	11.915	<0.001**
Q2. Unasyn is administered by slow IV injection over at least 10-15 min or infusion over 15-30 min	12(40.0%)	27 (90.0 %)	16.484	<0.001**
Q3. Inadequate duration of therapy contributes to antibiotic resistance due to or a poorly designed dosing regimen.	14(46.7%)	28 (93.3 %)	15.556	<0.001**
Q4. Do not mix ceftriaxone with IV solutions containing calcium because of the precipitation that can be formed	15(50.0%)	27 (90.0 %)	11.429	<0.001**
Q5. Claforan (cefotaxime) is a medication belongs to a class of drugs known as cephalosporin antibiotics	17(56.7%)	26(86.7)	6.648	0.010*

Q6. The possible side effect of Claforan is phlebitis	15(50.0%)	26(86.7)	9.320	0.002*
Q7. Ceftriaxone is given through IV push/bolus method	8(26.7%)	24(80.0)	17.143	<0.001**
Nurses' knowledge regarding intravenous antibiotic preparation				
Hands washing with antiseptic or alcohol rub should be performed before preparation of IV antibiotic solution/medication	15(50.0%)	27(90.0%)	11.429	0.001*
It is not necessary to check expiry date for a medication that is recently invented from pharmacy	8(26.7%)	28(93.3%)	27.778	0.001*
The Cefotaxime vial top should be swabbed with alcohol swabs prior to reconstitution with NaCl 0.9%	11(36.7%)	28(93.3%)	21.172	0.001*
Any reconstituted IV medications can still be used if it is less than 48 hours from the date of reconstitution or preparation	10(33.3%)	25(83.3%)	15.429	0.001*
IV antibiotics are stable when diluted using NaCl 0.9% or NaCl 3%	10(33.3%)	26(86.7%)	17.778	0.001*
nurses' knowledge regarding intravenous antibiotic administration				
Slow push \ bolus IV injection means administration of IV medication in 1 minute.	10(33.3%)	26(86.7%)	17.778	0.001*
Peripheral IV catheter sites should be inspected for phlebitis or extravasations during administration of IV push \ bolus antibiotics administration.	16(53.3%)	28(93.3%)	12.273	0.001*
Medication administered intramuscularly acts rapidly than if administered intravenously	15(50.0%)	25(83.3%)	7.500	0.001*
With time-critical medications such as early antibiotics or delayed administration of maintenance doses of more than 30 minutes before or after the scheduled dose will most likely cause harm	8(26.7%)	22(73.3%)	13.067	0.001*
Nurses can administer medications identified as non–time-critical within 1 to 2 hours of their scheduled time	14(46.7%)	29(96.7%)	18.468	0.001*
Nurses' knowledge regarding complications arising from IV antibiotic via push/bolus				
Antibiotics might develop allergy in susceptible individuals and sometimes lead to death	16(53.3%)	28(93.3%)	12.273	0.001*
The following combined manifestation may indicate an allergic reaction: Rash, itching, difficulty swallowing or shortness of breath	16(53.3%)	27(90.0%)	9.932	0.001*

In case of prescribing antibiotics for the patient. The nurse should check the PTT test	9(30.0%)	24(80.0%)	15.152	0.001*
Total Knowledge				
Unsatisfactory	21(70.0%)	6(20.0%)	15.152	0.001*
Satisfactory	9(30.0%)	24(80.0%)		

Data is presented as frequency (%). * Significant P value < 0.05. t: Student t-test.

Nurses practice regarding preparing sterile water for injection from an ampule (preparing the medication) was significantly improved post-intervention than pre-intervention ($P < 0.05$) except for comparison the label of the medication with the MA didn't significantly improve. Nurses practice regarding preparing sterile water for injection from an ampule (preparing the ampule and following the steps) was significantly improved post-intervention than pre-intervention ($P < 0.05$). **Table 3**

Table 3: Comparison of nurses practice regarding preparing sterile water for injection from an ampule (preparing the medication, the ampule, following steps) pre and post implementation of safety guidelines

	Pre-intervention (n=30)	Post-Intervention (n=30)	χ^2	P
Preparing the medication				
Verified the health care provider's orders	24(80.0%)	30(100.0%)	6.667	0.010*
Performed hand hygiene and prepared supplies	4(13.3%)	20(66.7%)	17.778	0.001*
If using a medication cart, move it outside the patient's room. Unlocked the cart.	3(10.0%)	20(66.7%)	20.376	0.001*
Selected the ampule containing the correct drug from the medication cart or automated dispensing system. Compared the label of the medication with the MAR	15(50.0%)	22(73.3%)	3.455	0.063
Checked the expiration date and drug dose on the ampule	11(36.7%)	22(73.3%)	8.148	0.004*
Calculated the drug dose as necessary. Double checked calculation	4(13.3%)	20(66.7%)	17.778	0.001*
Preparing the ampoule				
Tap the top of the ampule lightly and quickly	5(16.7%)	20(66.7%)	15.429	0.001*
Placed a small gauze pad or unopened alcohol swab around the neck of the ampule	5(16.7%)	20(66.7%)	15.429	0.001*
Quickly and firmly snapped the neck of the ampule	2(6.7%)	20(22.7%)	23.254	0.001*
Drew up the medication	0(0.0%)	20(66.7%)	30.000	0.001*
Following steps				
Insert the filter needle into the center of the ampule opening. Did not allow the	3(10.0%)	20(66.7%)	20.376	0.001*

needle tip or the shaft to touch the rim of the ampule				
Aspirated medication into the syringe	15(50.0%)	22(73.3%)	34.55	0.001*
Keep the needle tip under the surface of the liquid. Tipped the ampule to bring all of the fluid within the needle	5(16.7%)	20(66.7%)	15.429	0.001*
To expel excess air bubbles, remove the needle from the ampule. Tapped the side of the syringe. Drew the plunger back slightly, and pushed the plunger upward to eject the air	3(10.0%)	20(66.7%)	20.376	0.001*
If the syringe contained excess fluid, use the sink for disposal. Slowly ejected the excess into the sink. Rechecked the fluid level in the syringe	3(10.0%)	20(66.7%)	20.376	0.001*
Covered the filter needle with its safety sheath and removed it from the syringe. Replaced the filter needle with a regular safety needle of the appropriate gauge and length	NP	NP	NP	NP
If medication was drawn away from the patient 'bedside, labeled the syringe with the name of the medication and the amount of medication it contains	4(13.3%)	20(66.7%)	17.778	0.001*
Disposed of soiled supplies. Placed the broken ampule and used filter needle/straw in a puncture-proof and leak-proof container. Cleaned work area, and performed hand hygiene	9(30.0%)	20(66.7%)	8.076	0.004*
If medication was drawn away from the patient 'bedside, labeled the syringe with the name of the medication and the amount of medication it contains	4(13.3%)	20(66.7%)	17.778	0.001*
Disposed of soiled supplies. Placed the broken ampule and used filter needle/straw in a puncture-proof and leak-proof container. Cleaned work area, and performed hand hygiene	9(30.0%)	20(66.7%)	8.076	0.004*

Data is presented as frequency (%). * Significant P value < 0.05. X2: Chi-square test.

Nurses' practice regarding preparing antibiotic from vial was significantly improved post-intervention than pre-intervention ($P < 0.05$), except for administration, based on prescribed route and checking medication order against the original order in the medical record didn't significantly improve. Nurses' practice regarding preparing section IV antibiotic administration via bolus or push was significantly improved post-intervention than pre-intervention ($P < 0.05$), except for withdrawing medication from ampule/ vial, transport medications and equipment to the patient, putting on clean gloves, uncapping syringe, steady port while inserting syringe into center of port and pulling back slightly on plunger just until blood appears in tubing didn't significantly improve. Total practice score was significantly improved post-intervention than pre-intervention ($P < 0.05$). **Table 4**

Table 4: Comparison of nurses' practice regarding preparing antibiotic from vial and s IV antibiotic administration via bolus or push pre and post implementation of safety guidelines

	Pre- Intervention (n=30)	Post- Intervention (n=30)	X ²	P
Gather equipment, check medication	15(50.0%)	25(83.3%)	7.500	0.006*
Know actions, dose, purpose, adverse effects and nursing consideration	1(3.3%)	29(96.7%)	52.267	<0.001*
Perform hand hygiene	0(0.0%)	29(96.7%)	56.129	<0.001*
Prepare administration in the medication area.	1(3.3%)	21(70.0%)	28.708	<0.001*
Unlock the medication cart or drawer	--	--	--	--
Prepare for one patient at a time	7(23.3%)	23(76.7%)	17.067	<0.001*
Read the MAR	15(50.0%)	27(90.0%)	11.429	<0.001*
Compare the label with the MAR, check expiration dates and perform calculations, if necessary, scan the bar code on the package, if required	1(3.3%)	20(66.7%)	26.447	<0.001*
Remove the metal or plastic cap on vial	25(83.3%)	30(100.0%)	5.455	0.020*
Swab the rubber top and allow it to dry	1(3.3%)	20(66.7%)	26.447	<0.001*
Remove the cap from the needle by pulling it straight, touch the plunger only, draw back an amount of air into the syringe equal to the required dose	15(50.0%)	27(90.0%)	11.429	<0.001*
Hold the vial on a flat surface, pierce the rubber stopper in the center with the needle tip and inject the measured air into the space above the solution	19(63.3%)	28(93.3%)	7.954	0.005*
Invert the vial. Keep the below the fluid level	16(53.3%)	30(100.0%)	18.261	<0.001*
Hold the vial in one hand, withdraw the medication, touch the plunger, draw medication holding the syringe vertically at eye level	23(76.7%)	30(100.0%)	7.925	0.005*
Tap the barrel sharply if the air is present. Return the needle tip to the solution and continue withdrawal of the medication	14(46.7%)	26(86.7%)	10.800	<0.001*
After the correct dose is withdrawn, replace the cap over the needle	22(73.3%)	28(93.3%)	4.320	0.038*
Check the amount of medication in the syringe with the medication dose and discard any surplus	22(73.3%)	30(100.0%)	9.231	0.002*
Recheck the label with CMAR/MAR	1(3.3%)	20(66.7%)	26.447	<0.001*
If a multi dose used, label the vial with date and time opened, and store the remaining	--	--	--	--
Lock the medication cart before leaving	0(0.0%)	20(66.7%)	30.000	<0.001*
Perform hand hygiene	3(10.0%)	20(66.7%)	20.376	<0.001*
Proceed with administration, based on prescribed route	28(93.3%)	30(100.0%)	2.069	0.150
Gather equipment	11(36.7%)	25(83.3%)	13.611	<0.001*
Check medication order against the original order in the medical record	30(100.0%)	30(100.0%)	0.000	1.000
Check the patient's chart for allergies	11(36.7%)	30(100.0%)	27.805	<0.001*

Verify medication and IV fluid	12(40.0%)	26(86.7%)	14.067	<0.001*
Section IV antibiotic administration via bolus or push				
Check a drug resource to clarify dilution before administration	2(6.7%)	22(73.3%)	27.778	<0.001*
Check the infusion rate.	22(73.3%)	30(100.0%)	9.231	0.002*
Know the actions, safe dose, purpose and adverse effects	1(3.3%)	22(73.3%)	31.093	<0.001*
Perform hand hygiene	0(0.0%)	20(66.7%)	30.000	<0.001*
Prepare medication outside of the patient's room	0(0.0%)	20(66.7%)	30.000	<0.001*
Unlock the medication cart	--	--	--	--
Prepare for one patient at a time	3(10.0%)	23(76.7%)	27.149	<0.001*
Read the CMAR/MAR and select the proper medication from drawer	10(33.3%)	30(100.0%)	30.000	<0.001*
Compare the label with CMAR/MAR	0(0.0%)	20(66.7%)	30.000	<0.001*
Check expiration dates and perform calculations, if necessary	0(0.0%)	20(66.7%)	30.000	<0.001*
Withdraw medication from ampule /vial	23(76.7%)	27(90.0%)	1.920	0.166
Recheck the label with the MAR before taking it to the patient	4(13.3%)	21(70.0%)	19.817	<0.001*
Lock the medication cart before leaving	3(10.0%)	21(70.0%)	22.500	<0.001*
Transport medications and equipment to the patient's bedside and keep in sight	30(100.0%)	30(100.0%)	0.000	1.000
Ensure that the patient receives the medications at the correct time	10(33.3%)	21(70.0%)	8.076	0.004*
Perform hand hygiene and put on PPE	4(13.3%)	22(73.3%)	21.991	<0.001*
Identify the patient using two methods. Compare information CMAR/MAR	6(20.0%)	20(66.7%)	13.303	<0.001*
Ask the patient's name and birth date	3(10.0%)	20(66.7%)	20.376	<0.001*
Close the door or pull the curtain	1(3.3%)	20(66.7%)	26.447	<0.001*
Perform assessments before administering medications.	1(3.3%)	20(66.7%)	26.447	<0.001*
Check the patient's allergy bracelet or ask the patient about allergies	1(3.3%)	20(66.7%)	26.447	<0.001*
Explain the purpose and action of the medication to the patient	1(3.3%)	20(66.7%)	26.447	<0.001*
Assess IV site for inflammation or infiltration	12(40.0%)	30(100.0%)	25.714	<0.001*
If IV infusion pump pause the pump	--	--	--	--
Put on clean gloves	15(50.0%)	21(70.0%)	2.500	0.114
Select the injection port on tubing that is closest to venipuncture site. Clean port with antimicrobial swab.	3(10.0%)	20(66.7%)	20.376	<0.001*
Uncap syringe. Steady port while inserting syringe into center of port	21	26	2.455	0.117
Move your hand to the section of IV tubing just above the injection port	15	26	9.320	0.002*
Fold the tubing between your fingers.	15	26	9.320	0.002*
Pull back slightly on plunger just until blood appears in tubing	21	27	3.750	0.053
Inject medication at recommended rate	0	20	30.000	<0.001*
Release the tubing	12	25	11.915	<0.001*
Remove the syringe and do not recap	12	25	11.915	<0.001*

Engage safety shield or needle guard	12	25	11.915	<0.001*
Release tubing to allow IV flow	12	30	25.714	<0.001*
Discard needle and syringe in receptacle	12	28	19.200	<0.001*
Check IV fluid infusion rate.	0	20	30.000	<0.001*
Restart infusion pump, if appropriate	13	20	3.300	0.069
Remove gloves and additional PPE	13	23	6.944	0.008*
Perform hand hygiene	13	28	17.330	<0.001*
Document administration immediately	8	20	9.643	0.002*
Evaluate the patient's response	3	20	20.376	<0.001*
Total practice score				
Unsatisfactory	24(80.0%)	7(23.3%)	19.288	<0.001*
Satisfactory	6(20.0%)	23(76.7%)		

Data is presented as frequency (%). * Significant P value < 0.05. X²: Chi-square test.

Nurse's attitude was significantly improved post-intervention than pre-intervention (P<0.05). **Table 5**

Table 5: Comparison of nurse's attitude pre and post implementation of safety guidelines

	Pre-intervention (n=30)	Post-Intervention (n=30)	X ²	P
Recent scientific evidence should be considered for some reliable guidelines for the safe preparation and administration of intravenous antibiotics	10(33.3%)	22(73.3%)	9.643	0.002*
IV Push/Bolus administration errors should be reported	10(33.3%)	22(73.3%)	9.643	0.002*
Nursing skills about safe IV push/bolus administration should be evaluated	11(36.7%)	24(80.0%)	11.589	0.001*
Protocols/ guidelines/ procedures can affect professional behavior, ensuring proper management of IV push/bolus	13(43.3%)	22(73.3%)	5.554	0.018*
Awareness of error prevention and clinical risk management errors during preparation	11(36.7%)	21(70.0%)	6.696	0.010*
Ongoing and specific training on safe management of administration could reduce the risk of error	13(43.3%)	22(73.3%)	5.554	0.018*
If I saw a colleague make an error, I would keep it to myself	10(33.3%)	22(73.3%)	9.643	0.002*
If there is no harm for a patient, there is no need to address an error	12(40.0%)	21(70.0%)	5.455	0.020*
There is a gap between what we define as "evidence-based practices" and what we provide patients daily regarding the safe preparation and administration of intravenous antibiotics (Push/Bolus method)	14(46.7%)	23(76.7%)	5.711	0.017*
Healthcare professionals routinely share information about Preparation and safe administration of intravenous antibiotics (Push/Bolus method)	9(30.0%)	21(70.0%)	9.600	0.002*

Data is presented as frequency (%). * Significant P value < 0.05. X²: Chi-square test.

DISCUSSION

Patient safety is the avoidance of unintended or unexpected harm to people during the provision of health care (National Health Service, 2020).

The findings of the study regarding nurses' knowledge of intravenous antibiotic preparation pre and post implementation of safety guidelines agreed with Mezaache et al. [13] about a two-component intervention to improve hand hygiene practices and promote alcohol-based hand rub use among people who inject drugs: a mixed-methods evaluation. Who reported that pre-intervention 14% of participants reported never performing hand hygiene, while post-intervention, 50 and 61% of participants reported adopting hand hygiene.

Regarding intravenous antibiotic administration pre and post implementation of safety guidelines, pre intervention, The findings showed a clear improvement in nurses' knowledge and practice after the education intervention as the comparison of pre- and post-intervention as the current study finding revealed that there was a high significant difference in the total knowledge score of nurses regarding all items of intravenous antibiotic administration pre and post implementation of safety guidelines. This was in the same line with Faris and Abed [14] reported in their pre-test prior to their educational program implementation that; all nurses had an unsatisfactory knowledge level concerning parenteral IV medication administration. As well as, the result agrees with Ping Lim Wong et al., (2018) and Lamsal, & Shrestha, (2019) in their study about knowledge and practice of nurses regarding IVT who found that the significant difference after administration of their training in a teaching hospital.

In reference to nurses' knowledge regarding complication arising from IV antibiotics via push/bolus pre and post implementation, there was a high significant difference in the total knowledge score of nurses about all items of complications arising from IV antibiotic via push/bolus pre and post implementation of safety guidelines. This current study agrees with a study done by Dhungana, Bajracharya and Reynolds, [15] revealed that most of the the nurse's post intervention correctly answered the actions required for cannula site redness and swelling,

Concerning satisfactory level of total knowledge level, the current study finding showed that there is a significant increase in total knowledge level. This point of view is supported with Ismail and Ismail, [16] revealed that the mean score of total knowledge was increased post guidelines implementation than before. Also, there were highly significant differences between all items of knowledge.

The current study showed that majority of staff nurses had a low level of practice regarding safety guidelines, where it improved to be all of staff nurses had high level post program. This current finding agreed with Dhungana, Bajracharya, Reynolds, [15] documented that only one nurse informed the patient or attendant about the medication under use and its possible adverse effects. Very few nurses (16.5%) checked the medication site for proper cannula placement, patency, leakage and phlebitis. While 72.2% of nurses properly administered the medication (slowly and gently for bolus and

with calculated drop rate for infusion), 53.9% discarded the syringe in puncture-proof container. Only 20.9% washed their hands after medication administration.

The current study finding illustrated that there was a high statistically significant difference for most steps in nurses practice regarding preparing antibiotic from vial pre and post implementation of Safety Guidelines. The current study finding matched with Abd Elgwad, Abdallah and Khalil, ^[17] reported that, in relation to the satisfactory level of practice regarding all components of medication safety guidelines, the current study results revealed that; the majority of the nurses studied had got a highly significant improvement in their practice regarding medication administration process post application of the medication safety guidelines. This current finding contradicted with Dhungana, Bajracharya, and Reynolds, ^[15] documented that almost all nurses verified the medication order using patient's chart, but only one nurse assessed the patient's history of drug allergies. High proportion of nurses (88, 76.5%) confirmed the right patient by checking the prescription sheet, but only 20 nurses (17.4%) verified it by checking the patient's identity card or calling out his/her name. While 72.2% of nurses properly administered the medication, 53.9% discarded the syringe in puncture-proof container. Only 20 nurses (20.9%) washed their hands after medication administration. As well as in an accordance study conducted by Jafaru & Abubakar, ^[18] showed that most of the respondents in this study did not identify the allergic patient in two or more ways, with a bracelet and a medical record for instance. Finally, the current study finding showed that there was a high significant difference in the total nurses practice score pre and post implementation of Safety Guidelines, in which the majority of studied nurses has unsatisfactory level of total nurses practice pre implementation of safety guidelines which decreased to less than one third of studied nurses has unsatisfactory level of total nurses practice post-implementation of safety guidelines.

Nurses' attitude after receiving IV push/ bolus antibiotic administration safety guidelines will differ from their pre safety guidelines total attitude mean scores. The current study finding clarified that there was significant difference in nurse's attitude pre and post implementation of safety guidelines, since pre-intervention the current study reported that near half of nurses have negative attitude regarding medication administration. This current finding agreed with the current study findings, Escandell-Rico et al. ^[19] claimed that the study subjects in their research have an unfavorable attitude towards reporting errors.

The current study finding showed that the majority of the nurses studied has an unsatisfactory level of attitude pre implementation of safety guidelines, while more than two third of the nurses studied report satisfactory level of attitude post implementation of safety guidelines. This current finding matched with Abu Hussein, Elsaied, and Ghandour, ^[20] showed that nearly two thirds of staff nurses had a good attitude regarding medication administration, where it improved to be nearly half of staff nurses had very good attitude post program.

Limitations of the study included that the sample size was relatively small. The study was in a single center.

CONCLUSIONS

Intravenous antibiotic push administration safety guidelines had a positive effect on nurses' performance, so it is recommended that IV push antibiotic administration safety guidelines be applied in all health care facilities to achieve high quality patient care.

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